

Cybercrime - Financial fraud on the person - Social Networks

Arthur Victoria

Previous Note

Article 10 of the General Tax Law makes it clear that the unlawful nature of obtaining income does not preclude its taxation when the acts or facts that gave rise to it satisfy the applicable incidence assumptions.

We understand that criminal activities of cybercrime should be taxed income from criminal or civil, regardless of their illegal action.

Introduction

So-called social networks are a set of connections that directly or indirectly connect each member of a group to another group.

Social networks are a complex set of dynamizing interrelationships.

The human being has been strengthening relations and becoming increasingly communicative.

They are communication networks involving symbolic language, cultural boundaries, power relations, as well as the action of local solidarity networks in the fight against social exclusion.

Respecting the differences in the meanings attributed by individuals to work and loneliness, as well as the dimensions of organizations and management models, we must reflect on the faces of loneliness in the context of contemporary work, contemplating it:

1. as the affect of coexistence and social interaction;
2. as a symptom of malaise at work, the result of managerial ideology;
3. as a source for the development, invigoration, and formation of the individual.

Looking at loneliness, in this sense, refers to the affective bonds that work as a social construction can offer.

As a space for socialization, the individual builds, identifies, and is subjective at work.

The gaze of the other (the colleague, the client, the manager, the boss) contributes to the relaxation of the anxiety that loneliness can generate.

Regarding the relationship between groups of society, it can be stated that, often, due to the globalized world, face-to-face communication has become less effective and frequent.

Hence as a resource, the "loner" seeks other types of relationships that fill their social and convivial void. Linked to shyness and anonymity, she takes refuge in particular social networks that allow her to meet with whom to interact and dialogue virtually.

In this context, information can be shared and commented, and specific groups can be formed, leisure time among many other functions, all with a high possibility of visualization.

People's expectations of human/computer interaction are often inherent in what they expect from human/human interaction. Even clashing with the real meaning of the face-to-face relationship, the virtual provides interaction of people from different groups, i.e., from different hierarchical levels, social classes.

This form of relationship can bring several harms, because the individual runs away from reality, from his real identity, creates a fake profile, manipulates other people, deludes himself and can bring physical and mental harm.

The individual uses profiles to create a network of relationships that, most of the time, never got personal contact.

However, people who suffer from personal relationship difficulties, get through the internet the ease of interaction.

As a result, we find that the lonely or shy person has virtual tools to interact and relate with others, choosing the profile of the one who understands to be the ideal interlocutor.

Social networks can be divided into three strands:

- Primary or Informal Social Network: These are networks of relationships between individuals, due to pre-existing connections, semi-formalized relationships that give rise to almost groups. It is formed by all the links that people establish during daily life, which can be composed of family, neighbors, friends, co-workers. Relationship networks begin in childhood and contribute to the formation of identities.
- Secondary or Global Social Network: It consists of professionals and employees from public or private institutions, non-governmental organizations, social organizations, etc., and provides attention, guidance, and information.
- Intermediate Social Network or Associative Network: is formed by people who have received specialized training, with the function of prevention and support. They may come from the health sector, the church, and even the community itself.

The dating sites

Dating sites are a web-based service that allows individuals to build a public or semi-public profile within a limited system.

They can't articulate a list of other users with whom they share a call, view and browse their call list, and those made by other people within the system.

What makes dating sites unique is not that they allow individuals to meet strangers, but instead that they enable users to make them visible on their social networks.

As results appear in connections between individuals that would not be made but often not the goal, and these meetings are frequently between "latent" ties that share some offline connection.

At many of the major, dating sites participants are not necessarily networking or looking to meet new people; instead, they are primarily for communicating with people who are already a part of your social network.

A fundamental element of the organization of these sites, which has been dubbed "social networking sites."

Online Dating

Currently, over 40% of single men have used an app or a dating site in the last 30 days. There are many dating apps available operating in countries with higher membership in some regions.

Although they can cause a lot of trouble, in most cases, the perpetrators of scams study the profiles of their victims and collect personal information such as work activity, income level, or lifestyle they have.

One of the most common situations is the contact with a scammer who emotionally manipulates his victim into sending him money, gifts, or personal information.

Another prevalent type of scam is sexual racketeering, which usually begins as a reasonable relationship between two people until the scammer tries to get out of the conversation on the dating platform to use, for example, WhatsApp.

On this other platform, the perp tries to convince the victim to upload spicy photos or intimate videos and then use this obscene material to blackmail the victim.

Another well-known scam is catfishing, which lures the victim into a relationship based on the criminal's fictional online personality.

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Now, with the technological evolution of "Cyber crime" linked to artificial intelligence comes the creation of fake profiles that use third party photographs, creating diverse profiles for all tastes and ages.

The innovator is the absence of the traditional blow to the victim but the fraud practiced in two ways:

- The user, signing up freely on the site and building his profile, is immediately contacted by several users who compliment him and ask questions about himself. Therefore it is required to send the response to the request. The user has to buy a pack of messages for 12 Euros, purchase of Credits by bank transfer, or credit card, allowing you to send ten messages.

- You grant Notify Direct Marketing B.V. permission to use your intellectual property rights in the content provided by You. This permission includes the company explicitly "Notify Direct Marketing BV's" the right to duplicate, make available, modify, translate, scan, use for advertising, commercial or non-commercial purposes, sublicense, or transfer content related to Profiles (information, photos, images descriptions, search criteria, etc.).

- Notify Direct Marketing B.V. expressly reserves the right to make contacts on flerteeligue.com through fictitious profiles you create with which no physical connections are possible.

Cyber fraud

These items, as mentioned above, are on the site in a link that refers - contractual, multi-page conditions, along with other relationships such as contact, help, and others.

That is, the user, by signing up certainly as on dozens of other sites of this type rarely reads the various pages of the Terms of Use. That is, all communication with all fake profiles that use photographs of other companies of the kind (referred to in the "Terms of Use" this exchange of profiles and photos), will make available the use of your photo and data for all purposes by the referred company.

Also, access to your payment cards is the property of the same company may be legally granted to third parties.

And because in this company monthly sells more than 200,000 Euros of message packages, although it is said to be subject to VAT taxation and the Netherlands is a country with special tax regime, it makes national capital paid out of legal control.

Interesting to mention the use of artificial intelligence logarithms to maintain exciting conversations with the user sending him many replies and chat messages spending hundreds of Euros daily.

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